

CPTM Model for DevSecOps

C12-Difficulties in integrating security into DevOps without losing speed

- P19-Shifting security to the left
- P20-Security-by-Design
- P50-Design-as-Code
 - ✦ M03-Time spent correcting mistakes in each category
 - ✦ M05-SLA performance
 - ✦ M08-Number of continuous delivery cycles per month

C13-Difficulties in transforming to DevSecOps without affecting current process

- P19-Shifting security to the left
- P20-Security-by-Design
- P50-Design-as-Code
 - ✦ M05-SLA performance
 - ✦ M08-Number of continuous delivery cycles per month

C14-Compliance requirements

- P23-Compliance control
- P51-Compliance-as-Code
 - ◆ Tools: nspec, ServerSpec, OpenSCAP

C15-Neglecting change control in security

- P22-Good documentation, logging and reporting
 - ◆ Logging Tools: PaperTrail, Logstash, Loggly, Splunk, SumoLogic

C16-Lack of standards

- P33-Common weaknesses enumeration
 - ✦ M02-Top vulnerability

C17-Ignoring processes and security essentials leading to technical and security debt

- P25-Vulnerability and incident management
 - ◆ Tools: Defect Dojo, ArcherySec, Snyk, HackerOne, Claire, Stethoscope, Rapid7 Nexpose
- P56-Sensitive information scans
 - ◆ Tools: TruffleHog, GitSecrets, Talisman
- P31-Security review and evaluation
 - ◆ Tools: Tripwire, Snort
- M04-Security review performance
- P24-Risk management
 - ✦ M06-Critical risk profiling
 - ✦ M07-Point of risk per device

C18-Lacking process and platform for communication, collaboration, and sharing information and feedback

- P02-Improving collaboration, communication and cooperation

C19-Out-of-sync domains and cross team dependencies causing issues in adopting DevSecOps

- P29-Define security requirements
 - ✦ M16-Whether automated testing covers security requirements

C20-Using unsuitable metrics

- P30- Define metrics
- P27-Software process maturity
 - ◆ DevOps Measuring Tool: SAFe DevOps Health Radar
 - ✦ M18-Use of SAFe DevOps Health Radar

C21-Tradeoff between security measures and CI system performance

- P34-Operational controls validation and improvement
- P31-Security review and evaluation
 - ◆ Tools: Tripwire, Snort
 - ✦ M04-Security review performance

C22-Interconnectedness of the DevOps process

- P19-Shifting security to the left
- P20-Security-by-Design
- P50-Design-as-Code
 - ✦ M08-Number of continuous delivery cycles per month

C23-Continuous deployment chaos

- P41-Fault injection (chaos engineering)
 - ✦ M13-Penetration test pass rate

C24-Poor visibility of security track record

- P21-Increase the visibility
- P22-Good documentation, logging and reporting
 - ◆ Logging Tools: PaperTrail, Logstash, Loggly, Splunk, SumoLogic

C25-Inadequate privileged credentials and access controls causing cyber attacks

- P26-Privilege management
- P32-Keep credentials safe

C01-Cultural resistance and organizational opposition

- P01-Cultural shift to security
- P02-Improving collaboration, communication and cooperation
- P08- Continuous feedback loop
- P10-Trust
- P11-Shameless retrospectives

C02-Challenges of collaboration, communication and coordination

- P06-Security champions
- P09-Make security a priority

C04-Lack of security awareness and responsibility

- P03-Shared and collective responsibility for security
- P14-Pragmatic implementation
- P15-Be reactive and responsive

C05-Lack of security knowledge and skills, need for training

- P04-Shared knowledge
- P05-Training, learning and education for security
 - ✦ M01-Security-trained rate

C06-Boundary between specialist & generalist

- P04-Shared knowledge

C07-Insufficient level of governance on DevSecOps adoption

- P13-Enhance transparency
- P16-Security policies

C08-Recruiting challenges

- P07-Recruiting success

C09-Inconsistent security polices design

- P16-Security policies
- P49-Policy-as-Code

C10-Challenges in decision level

- P16-Security policies
- P18-Leadership support

C11-Lacking confidence

- P12-Commitment and agreement
- P17-Continuous improvement mindset
- P18-Leadership support

C26-Lack of mature tools for automation and security

- P36-Automation
 - ◆ Tools: Chef, Jenkins, Ansible, Puppet, Gauntlt, SaltStack
- P43-DAST
 - ◆ Tools: OWASP ZAP, BDD Security, Arachini, Nikto, Radamsa, FuzzDB, Fortify Webspect
 - ✦ M14-Security test pass rate

P44-RASP

- ◆ Tool: Fortify Application Defender
- ✦ M14-Security test pass rate

P45-SAST

- ◆ Tools: Kiuwan, Flawfinder, Graudit, Bandit, Spotbugs, SonarQube
- ✦ M14-Security test pass rate

P46-IAST

- ✦ M14-Security test pass rate

P40-Red team security drills

- ✦ M19-Number of issues during red teaming drills

P53-Advanced malware detection

- ◆ Tool: CodeAI

P55-Secure coding

- ◆ Automated code review tools: Veracode Greenlight, PMD, DevSkim, FindSecBugs
- ✦ M15-Code scanning detection rate

C27-Challenges of legacy system refactoring

- P37-Security-as-Code
- P59-Integrate security issues within your general bug tracker

C28-Use of cloud and serverless computing brings security complications

- P39-Continuous monitoring
 - ◆ Tools: Suricata, NewRelic, Nagios Icinga, Graphite, Ganglia, Cacti, Pager Duty, Sensu, Boundry, Pingdom
- P56-Sensitive information scans
 - ◆ Tools: TruffleHog, GitSecrets, Talisman

P58-Verify cloud infrastructure

- ◆ Tools: Terraform, AppScan on Cloud, AWS Security service, ThreatModeler Cloud Edition, Trend Micro Cloud One

P28-MUSA security DevOps framework for multi-cloud applications

- P35-Hybrid life cycles with data-security focus
- P47-CI/CD for patching

P52-Adopting DevSecOps in microservices-based applications (8)

- P54-Micro-segmentation

C29-Threat modeling scalability issue

- P38-Threat modeling
 - ◆ Tools: IriusRisk, Microsoft threat modeling tool
 - ✦ M09-Number of adversaries per application
 - ✦ M10-Adversary return rate

C30- Containers and other tools come with their own risks

- P42-Container security
 - ◆ Container tools: Docker, Kubernetes
 - ◆ Container security tools: Twistlock, Notary, Aqua Security
- P56-Sensitive information scans
 - ◆ Tools: TruffleHog, GitSecrets, Talisman

P57-Software Composition Analysis

- ◆ Tools: Retire.js, OSSAudit, OWASP Dependency-Check
- ✦ M11-Defect density
- ✦ M12-Defect burn rate

C31-Complexity in managing different tools

- P36-Automation
 - ◆ Tools: Chef, Jenkins, Ansible, Puppet, Gauntlt, SaltStack

C32-Difficulty in simulating production

- P38-Threat modeling
 - ◆ Tools: IriusRisk, Microsoft threat modeling tool
 - ✦ M09-Number of adversaries per application
 - ✦ M10-Adversary return rate

C33-Availability and reliability of infrastructure resources, tools, automation, and network bandwidth for fast deployment cycle

- P39-Continuous monitoring
 - ◆ Tools: Suricata, NewRelic, Nagios Icinga, Graphite, Ganglia, Cacti, Pager Duty, Sensu, Boundry, Pingdom

P58-Verify cloud infrastructure

- ◆ Tools: Terraform, AppScan on Cloud, AWS Security service, ThreatModeler Cloud Edition, Trend Micro Cloud One

P48-Immutable-as-Code

- P54-Micro-segmentation
- P60-Configuration management
 - ✦ M17-Use of preapproved libraries, packages, tool chains, and processes

C34-Challenges of cost control

- P65-Linear scalability and affordable cost
 - ✦ M20-Business metrics (revenue and KPIs)

C35-Conflicts between security and business

- P63-Separation of duties
- P64-Business-driven security
 - ✦ M20-Business metrics (revenue and KPIs)

C36-Customer readiness for frequent releases

- P61-Big data and behavioral analytic techniques
- P66-Availability and business continuity management

C37-Difficulty in training users for using advanced tools

- P62-Consumable security services with APIs

